

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE UNSUSPECTED WATER DISSOCIATION CAPACITY OF INTRAVENTRICULAR CHOROID PLEXUSES AND CHOROID LAYER OF THE EYE. IMPLICATIONS IN THE BIOLOGY AND EMBRYOLOGY OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM AND THE EYEBALL

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Abstract

Until now, the biodynamics of cerebrospinal fluid (Production, reabsorption, composition) had been a mystery that was tried to be explained by theories that included somewhat imaginary mechanisms such as ultrafiltration. Although it was not specified at what level or in what part of the cell membrane it happened, since this entirely theoretical mechanism requires the presence of tiny pores that resist the significant energy required to push liquids through them.

But the structures of the cell do not tolerate high pressures without being destroyed, nor can such high pressures be generated inside the cells, since both proposals would require high amounts of energy.

On the other hand, both the composition and intraventricular pressure of CSF are astonishingly constant, with variations within relatively narrow ranges. Facts that cannot be easily explained either.

Our observation about the existence of molecules inside human eukaryotic cells, capable of transforming the power of light into chemical energy by dissociating water molecules, as in plants; it is a disruptive knowledge that offers a logical option regarding the biodynamics of the CSF with important implications in the biology of the CNS.

Keywords: Aqueous humor, CSF, dissociation, endergonic, exergonic, hydrogen, CNS, oxygen, sunlight.

Background

Current physiology and therefore medicine is characterized by being full of theories that are based on a dogma that dates back to the eighteenth century, which refers to the mistaken belief that our body obtains oxygen from the air that surrounds it, through inspiration, which crosses the walls of the pulmonary alveolus by simple diffusion to reach the bloodstream and from there be distributed to all the cells of the body. And all this is explained by theoretical mechanisms, starting with the entirely theoretical Krogh's mathematical model in relation to gas exchange in the lung [1].

Supposedly, the main purpose of respiration is to provide oxygen to the cells at a rate adequate to satisfy their metabolic needs. This involves transport of oxygen from the lung to the tissues by means of the circulation of blood. Theoretically, each cell maintains a set of furnaces, the mitochondria, where, through the oxidation of foodstuffs such as glucose, the energetic needs of the cells are supplied. Supposedly, the precise object of respiration is the supply of oxygen to mitochondria. [2]

Gas exchange is highly efficient within the limited space of the thoracic cavity because the tree-like airway system greatly enlarges the contact surface between blood vessels and airways. And spite the typical human lung tree undergoes 23 generations of dichotomous branching [3] The relatively low amount of oxygen in the atmosphere cannot meet the metabolic requirements of cells, which, in proportion, contain almost five times more oxygen.

Therefore, after almost three hundred years, the therapeutical results, based majorly on theories and mathematical models, have not been what the patients need.

Introduction

The Eye is the only place in the body where both neurons, melanin, and blood vessels can be seen directly (Figure 1), thereby, the use of the eye as a window into changes in the brain is rapidly increasing in research. The results of these studies impact on both the understanding of the effects of neurological diseases on vision and the possibility of using eye tests to detect or monitor systemic diseases.

¹ Gjedde A. Diffusive insights: on the disagreement of Christian Bohr and August Krogh at the Centennial of the Seven Little Devils. *Adv Physiol Educ.* 2010 Dec;34(4):174-85. doi: 10.1152/advan.00092.2010. PMID: 21098384.

² Reynolds A, Bard Ermentrout G, Clermont G. A mathematical model of pulmonary gas exchange under

inflammatory stress. *J Theor Biol.* 2010 May 21;264(2):161-73. doi: 10.1016/j.jtbi.2010.01.011. Epub 2010 Jan 18. PMID: 20083125; PMCID: PMC2856815.

³ R. Clement *et al.* Branching geometry induced by lung self-regulated growth. *Physical Biology* (2012).

The eye is an anatomical extension of the brain, and many similarities can be found between them. Multidisciplinary research of the brain or the eye will cross-fertilize each other, especially in the context of neurodegenerative diseases. As an extension of the telencephalon, the optic nerve is surrounded by the

meninges and cerebrospinal fluid, just like the brain. Furthermore, both tissues have highly melanized structures, the choroidal plexus in the brain and the choroidal layer in the eye.

Figure 1) Optic nerve on the left side. The tiny blood vessels that enter and leave the eyeball through the optic nerve, whose average diameter is 1200 microns, can be seen. The yellow arrow indicates the presence of melanin on the temporal side of the optic disc.

In some cases, or circumstances, it is not easy to determine whether visual symptoms are caused by brain disease or eye condition.

For instance, the theory that glaucoma is a two-pressure disease, which was supported by studies on astronauts, who often exhibit visual disturbances with swelling of the eye disc [4]. Understanding the balance between intraocular pressure, cerebrospinal fluid pressure, and systemic blood pressure is key to better management of diseases such as glaucoma and intracranial hypertension.

The Choroid Plexus

The choroid plexus (CP) can be seen anywhere throughout the ventricular system except for the cerebral aqueduct (Figure 2). It consists of numerous capillary-rich villi (with a blood flow of nearly ten times that of the cerebral cortex) (quite like the eye), which in turn are composed of a type of ependymal cells. The purpose of the choroid is to supposedly serve as a sort of filtration system for the ventricular system and the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). The most apparent location of the CP is the glomus, located within the trigones (atria) of the lateral ventricles. The CP is typically contiguous through the ventricular system,

⁴ SHENG, J., Q. LI, T. LIU and X. WANG (2022): Cerebrospinal fluid dynamics along the optic nerve. *Front. Neurol.* 13, 931523. 10.3389/fneur.2022.931523

Figure 2) Yellow arrow is signaling the choroid plexus, inside the ventricles.

Characteristically, in both organs, such structures are characterized by being made up of many capillaries, as well as significant amounts of melanin, in addition to being close to or even surrounded by significant

amounts of water. (Figure 3). Both structures (choroidal plexus and the choroidal layer of the eyeball) are constantly crossed by an intense blood flow, almost 10 times greater than the cerebral cortex.

Figure 3) The choroidal layer of the eyeball (yellow arrow) is covered by the sclera, and in its inner part it is in contact with a thin layer of photoreceptors, called the retina because of its lattice shape, to which it continuously provides oxygen and hydrogen from the dissociation of water molecules, a process that occurs strictly inside the melanin granules [5].

Choroid plexus is present in all four ventricles. The main function of the choroid plexus is to produce cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) so far by unknown mechanisms and help regulate its composition. CSF is a clear fluid (like aqueous humor) that surrounds the brain and spinal cord, providing essential functions such as cushioning and protecting the brain from trauma, supplying nutrients, removing waste products, and maintaining a stable chemical environment.

Theoretically, choroid plexus achieves these functions through a combination of filtration, secretion, and selective transport. Supposedly, it filters blood plasma and selectively transports certain substances into CSF while removing waste products and excess ions. The choroid plexus also helps maintain the balance of ions and fluid within the CSF, ensuring proper neuronal functioning.

CSF is mainly composed of water (99%) (Table 1).

⁵ Herrera, AS., and Arias Esparza, Md., 2025. The unsuspected ability of the human cell to oxygenate itself. Applications in cell biology. Medical Research Archives, [online] 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.18103/mra.v13i3.6344>

Table 1)

Chemical composition of plasma, aqueous humor, and CSF. [6]

Component	Plasma	Aqueous	CSF	Units	Humor
HCO3	26	22	21	mmol/L	
Ca 2+	4.9	2.5	2.3	mmol/L	
Cl-	107	131	130	mmol/L	
Glucose	5.9	2.8	6	mmol/L	
Lactate	1.9	2.8	1.6	mmol/L	
Mg 2+	1.2	1.2	1.7	mmol/L	
PO4	1.1	0.5	0,6	mmol/L	
K+	4.6	2.2	2.9	mmol/L	
Na+	148	152	147	mmol/L	
Urea	7.3	6.1	7	mmol/L	
pH	7.4	7.2	7.3	pH scale	
Protein	7000	24	35	mg/dL	

The chemical composition as well as the physical characteristics of the CSF is similar to that of aqueous humor (Table 2), which was to be expected, given that the origin of both biological fluids come from tissues with very similar characteristics, that is: highly vascularized, fenestrated capillaries, high blood flow,

the amount of pigment is significant in both, and close to cavities with high water content, ventricles in the case of the choroidal plexuses, and vitreous humor in the case of the choroid in the eye.

Table 2) The similarities in chemical composition between plasma, aqueous humor, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) are more evident when we graph them.

The graph in relation to pH (Table 3) shows significant differences between the pH of blood plasma and that of aqueous humor and cerebrospinal fluid. Although such differences are based on the high

content of proteins and other molecules in the plasma, and in the case of aqueous humor and CSF, the differences would be explained by the different anatomy of the ventricles, as well as the difference in

⁶ M. Mamić, M. Matković, P. Dmitrović, V. Plichta and B. Pirkić. Dynamics between cerebrospinal fluid and aqueous humour – are they bidirectional? VETERINARSKA STANICA 56 (5), 663-670, 2025.

light exposure. And despite the different locations, the variation in pH between these liquids is relatively moderate or even slight.

Table 3) Body fluids pH is determined by the content of protons (H^+) generated from organic acids produced in living cells [7]. The word oxygen means acid former, one of the acids it forms is carbonic acid (CO_2)

The intracellular pH in most living cells is alkaline compared to the pH generated by protons that are transported passively through the plasma membrane by electrochemical forces. In addition to buffering systems such as the bicarbonate-carbonate system, protein-proton binding, and phosphoric acid, several membrane transporters are responsible for proton removal from the cytosol and play important roles in maintaining alkaline pH in cells [8].

The normal physiological pH of mammalian arterial blood is strictly maintained at 7.40; blood has

pH buffers such as Hb (hemoglobin) and albumin (table 4). A decrease of more than 0.05 units from the normal pH results in acidosis. The body fluids of diabetic patients are chronically acidic and exhibit characteristic ketoacidosis caused by an increased level of ketone bodies in the blood [9]. Acidic conditions can also result in physical fatigue of diabetic patients. The buffering capacity is relatively high in the cytosol and blood but low in the interstitial fluid due to limited buffering factors such as proteins [10].

Protein content in plasma, aqueous humor, and CSF, in mg/dL.

⁷ Aoi W, Marunaka Y. Importance of pH homeostasis in metabolic health and diseases: crucial role of membrane proton transport. *Biomed Res Int.* 2014;2014:598986. doi: 10.1155/2014/598986. Epub 2014 Sep 11. PMID: 25302301; PMCID: PMC4180894.

⁸ Poole RC, Halestrap AP. Transport of lactate and other monocarboxylates across mammalian plasma membranes. *The American Journal of Physiology—Cell Physiology.* 1993;264(4, part 1):C761–C782. doi: 10.1152/ajpcell.1993.264.4.C761.

⁹ Lemieux G, Aranda MR, Fournel P, Lemieux C. Renal enzymes during experimental diabetes mellitus in the rat. Role of insulin, carbohydrate metabolism, and ketoacidosis. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology.* 1984;62(1):70–75. doi: 10.1139/y84-010.

¹⁰ Fogh-Andersen N, Altura BM, Altura BT, Siggaard-Andersen O. Composition of interstitial fluid. *Clinical Chemistry.* 1995;41(10):1522–1525.

Table 4) The difference in protein content between plasma, aqueous humor, and CSF, is enormous, resulting in a lower buffering capacity of aqueous humor and CSF. Something like interstitial fluid.

The regulation of pH is through some different mechanisms when the amount, nature, and number of proteins is minimal, but in any case, energy is required for them to be carried out.

Carbonic Anhydrase

Both the aqueous humor (AH) and the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) are formed continuously. And in both cases reference is made to the diffusion, ultrafiltration (and the related dialysis), and active secretion. The observation of the existence of molecules capable of transforming the power of light

into chemical energy through the dissociation of water molecules, located intracellularly, and in plants, they explain in a coherent way the dynamics of both AH and CSF.

The administration of acetazolamide decreases the formation of aqueous humor and cerebrospinal fluid by up to 63% [11]. This maintains that the mechanisms of production of both biological fluids are similar, in addition to the fact that they come from tissues with very similar histological characteristics and therefore very similar functions.

Figure 4) Fundus images obtained with long-wave monochromatic light (<750 nm)

Observation of the ocular fundus with polychromatic (white) light allows us to obtain the usual images of the retina (optic nerve, blood vessels, casts, axes) (Figure 1). To study the choroid, it is necessary to use long wavelengths (red and infrared)

which yield images (figure 4) of the large number of blood vessels that make up the choroidal layer and intertwined between the blood vessels is melanin (dark, Latin) (Figure 5).

¹¹ Westgate CSJ, Kamp-Jensen C, Israelsen IME, Toft-Bertelsen T, Wardman JH, Jensen CA, Styrihave B, MacAulay N, Jensen RH, Eftekhari S. Acetazolamide and topiramate lower intracranial pressure through differential

mechanisms: The effect of acute and chronic administration. Br J Pharmacol. 2024 Jan;181(1):70-86. doi: 10.1111/bph.16213. Epub 2023 Sep 7. PMID: 37553842.

Figure 5) Microphotograph of a specimen of human choroid, stained with hematoxylin and eosin, 100 X; showing the large number of blood vessels (yellow star) in the choroidal layer of the eye, as well as the high concentration of melanin, which is located intracellularly; and that it reaches 40% more than in the skin. The blue arrow indicates the place where the photoreceptors (cones and rods) would be located.

Figure 6) Photographs taken with an endoscope in 1965 of the development of the human eye taken at 5 weeks, at the sixth and half weeks, and on the right, at the eighth week. [12]

Melanin is the fundamental molecule of life, since its unsuspected ability to transform the power of light into chemical energy, through the dissociation of water molecules, as in plants, constitutes a before and after in the origin of life, as it provides the oxygen (O₂),

hydrogen (H₂), reformed water, and high energy electrons that are required for the emergence of life. Hence, it is important that the pigmentation occurs early during embryogenesis.

¹² Nielssen, Lennart. <https://time.com/3876085/drama-of-life-before-birth-landmark-work-five-decades-later/>

Figure 7) The unsuspected intrinsic property of melanin of transforming the power of sunlight into chemical energy that can be used by living beings is through the dissociation of water molecules located inside the cell, and since it tolerates the high toxicity of oxygen, it is capable of reforming liquid water from oxygen and hydrogen, generating 4 high-energy electrons for every two water molecules reformed.

The fetus's heart rate reaches 170 beats per minute, and its breathing rate inside the uterus is about 20 breaths per hour, like fish; and at birth it rises to 20 breaths per minute, and yet the heart rate does not change.

The difference in respiratory rate is explained by the fact that water dilutes about 150 times more CO₂ than air, so that, during gestation, the embryo expels the CO₂ that each of its cells constantly produces into the amniotic fluid, through the lungs and digestive tract.

The hitherto unknown ability of eukaryotic cells to dissociate the molecule from water explains the origin of the oxygen with which the fish that possess it fill the swim bladder.

The importance of oxygen and hydrogen generation in embryogenesis

The new physiology (and biology) that will undoubtedly develop from the discovery that the human body (and any living entity) does not take oxygen from the environment that surrounds it (water,

air, or soil), but produces it by itself, highlights the importance of pigments in biology.

The dissociation of the molecule from water has the characteristics to be considered the basic or fundamental chemical reaction in relation to the origin of life, since it explains the interface between the living and the inanimate.

Hence, the appearance of pigments occurs rapidly during embryogenesis, while simultaneously forming, since the formation of the choroid layer in the outlines of the eye (Figure 6) occurs at the same time as the choroid plexuses of the cerebral ventricles (Figure 8, 9, 10). Since the formation of the tissues that make up the CNS and the eye, especially the retina, considered an extension of the CNS, are especially demanding of molecular hydrogen (H₂), molecular oxygen (O₂), reformed liquid water, and high-energy electrons; The main products of the dissociation of water that occurs inside pigmented molecules, especially in melanin.

Figure 8) Tissues with a higher amount of pigment, and highly vascularized, are prominent during gestation, since the requirements of hydrogen, oxygen, reformed water, and high-energy electrons are fundamental in the biochemical logic of tissues, especially those that are in formation.

Figure 9) The development of choroidal plexuses occurs in very early stages of CNS development, since the elements that derive from the dissociation of water (hydrogen (H_2), oxygen (O_2), reformed liquid water, and high-energy electrons), are fundamental for the development of surrounding tissues, and not a mere addition during gestation.

Figure 10) The presence of spaces with water very close to what we call intraventricular choroid plexuses, and the choroidal layer of the eye is characteristic.

It is feasible that the most pigmented embryonic cells develop first or at least more quickly since there is a greater availability of the elements resulting from the dissociation of water within them, and the surrounding tissues develop somewhat later, giving rise to the formation of very numerous capillaries between these pigmented cells, as well as the formation of spaces that ensure the availability of the main substrate: water, hence the formation of the cerebral ventricles in the case of the CNS, and of the vitreous, posterior, and anterior chambers of the eye.

Conclusion

The striking similarity in the graph in table 2, about the composition of plasma, aqueous humor, and cerebrospinal fluid, leads us to think that their origin is the same, referring to the dissociation of the molecule from water.

It is also noteworthy that the response of aqueous humor and CSF to the administration of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors is so similar, since in both cases the decrease in production is around 63%, what began

to be reported in the middle of the last century [13], and later confirmed by numerous works on the subject [14].

The mode of action of acetazolamide in the production of aqueous humor and CSF continues to be debated to date. well acetazolamide decreases the production of CSF but, in contrast to predictions based on studies in vitro, acetazolamide produces a marked increase in blood flow to choroid plexus. Thus, changes in blood flow to the choroid plexus and production of CSF are uncoupled after administration of acetazolamide [15].

Although there is no doubt about the action site [16] given that acetazolamide (AZE) effectively reduced the intracranial pressure (ICP), irrespective of the mode of drug administration and level of anesthesia. The effect appeared to occur via direct action on the choroid plexus and an associated decrease in cerebrospinal fluid secretion, and not indirectly via the systemic action of AZE on renal and vascular processes. Upon a single

administration, the reduced ICP endured for approximately 10 h post-AZE delivery with no long-term changes of brain water content or choroidal transporter expression. However, a persistent reduction of ICP was secured with repeated AZE administrations throughout the day.

Thereby, mode of action of acetazolamide on the choroidal plexus of CNS and choroidal layers of the eye will be better elucidated as the concept of the unsuspected ability of human eukaryotic cells to dissociate the molecule from water gradually spreads.

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¹³ Rubin, R. C., Henderson, E. S., Ommaya, A. K., Walker, M. D., & Rall, D. P. (1966). The Production of Cerebrospinal Fluid in Man and Its Modification by Acetazolamide. *Journal of Neurosurgery*, 25(4), 430-436. <https://doi.org/10.3171/jns.1966.25.4.0430>

¹⁴ Jafarzadeh F, Field ML, Harrington DK, Kuduvali M, Oo A, Kendall J, Desmond M, Mills K. Novel application of acetazolamide to reduce cerebrospinal fluid production in patients undergoing thoracoabdominal aortic surgery. *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2014 Jan;18(1):21-6. doi:

10.1093/icvts/ivt384. Epub 2013 Oct 14. PMID: 24130087; PMCID: PMC3867028.

¹⁵ Faraci FM, Mayhan WG, Heistad DD. Vascular effects of acetazolamide on the choroid plexus. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 1990 Jul;254(1):23-7. PMID: 2114478.

¹⁶ Barbuskaite, D., Oembo, E.K., Wardman, J.H. *et al*. Acetazolamide modulates intracranial pressure directly by its action on the cerebrospinal fluid secretion apparatus. *Fluids Barriers CNS* 19, 53 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12987-022-00348-6>